

Introduction of DS18B20 temperature sensor

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Temperature is one of the most basic environmental parameters. The measurement and control of temperature are of great significance and application value in people's daily life and industrial production. So, this paper realizes the temperature monitoring system based on STC MCU. The DS18B20 temperature sensor is used in the hardware, and the display circuit, temperature overrun alarm circuit and key input circuit are set up. Finally, according to the design of the system, the temperature measurement accuracy and stability are tested, and the results show that the measurement error of the system can be controlled within 1°C. in addition, the system has the characteristics of simple measurement, low cost and easy to use, good market prospects. DS18B20 temperature sensor is applied to the dynamic capacity increase of high voltage transmission lines to measure the conductor temperature and ambient temperature. The report is focused on the experiment of DS18B20 in the laboratory. From the result of the lab temperature measurement data analysis, using DS18B20's is the most suitable plan, considering both accuracy and economic efficiency. In the experiment, the data proved that DS18B20 has good stability, and small measurement error. It is suitable for measuring the temperature of conductor and ambient in dynamic capacity increase, and helpful to improve the accuracy of the calculation of capacity increasing.

Keyword: DS18B20 Temperature Sensor, Temperature Measurement display

1. Introduction

DS18B20 is 1-Wire digital temperature sensor from Maxim IC. Report's degrees in Celsius with 9 to 12-bit precision, from -55 to 125 (+/-0.5). Each sensor has a unique 64-Bit Serial

number etched into it - allows for a huge number of sensors to be used on one data bus. The DS18B20 is a 1-wire programmable Temperature sensor from maxim integrated. It is widely used to measure temperature in hard environments like in chemical solutions, mines or soil etc. It can measure a wide range of temperature from -55°C to $+125^{\circ}$ with a decent accuracy of $\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$. The core functionality of the DS18B20 is its direct-to-digital temperature sensor. The resolution of the temperature sensor is user-configurable to 9, 10, 11, or 12 bits, corresponding to increments of 0.5°C , 0.25°C , 0.125°C , and 0.0625°C , respectively. The default resolution at power-up is 12-bit.

1.1 Features:

- Unique 1-Wire interface requires only one port pin for communication
- Each device has a unique 64-bit serial code stored in an onboard ROM
- Multidrop capability simplifies distributed temperature sensing applications
- Requires no external components
- Can be powered from data line.
- Power supply range is 3.0V to 5.5V
- Measures temperatures from -55°C to $+125^{\circ}\text{C}$ (-67°F to $+257^{\circ}\text{F}$) $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ accuracy from -10°C to $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$
- Thermometer resolution is user-selectable from 9 to 12 bits
- Converts temperature to 12-bit digital word in 750ms (max.)
- User-definable non-volatile (NV) alarm settings
- Alarm search command identifies and addresses devices whose temperature is outside of programmed limits (temperature alarm condition)
- Applications include thermostatic controls, industrial systems, consumer products, thermometers, or any thermally sensitive system

1.2 Pin description

- GND - Ground
- DQ - Data In/Out
- VDD - Power Supply Voltage
- NC - No Connect

1.3 DS18B20 Pinout

DS18B20 has 3 pins in total, which are:

- Pin 1: Vcc (We have to provide +5V here).
- Pin 2: Data Pin (It's the 1-wire from where we will get temperature readings).
- Pin 3: GND (We have to provide ground here).

It is available in two packages, one is simple while the other one is waterproof DS18B20, both of their pinouts are shown in below figure:

1.4 Explanation

The DS18B20 Digital Thermometer provides 9 to 12-bit (configurable) temperature readings which indicate the temperature of the device. Information is sent to/from the DS18B20 over a 1-Wire interface, so that only one wire (and ground) needs to be connected from a central microprocessor to a DS18B20. Power for reading, writing, and performing temperature conversions can be derived from the data line itself with no need for an external power source.

Because each DS18B20 contains a unique silicon serial number, multiple DS18B20s can exist on the same 1-Wire bus. This allows for placing temperature sensors in many different places. Applications where this feature is useful include HVAC environmental controls, sensing temperatures inside buildings, equipment or machinery, and process monitoring and control system.

Table 1. Detailed Pin Description

Pin 8 PIN SOIC	Pin TO92	Symb ol	Description
5	1	GND	Ground
4	2	DQ	Data Input/Output pin. For 1-Wire operation: Open drain. (See “Parasite Power” section.)
3	3	V _{DD}	Optional VDD pin. See “Parasite Power” section for details of connection. VDD must be grounded for operation in parasite power mode.

2. Overview

The block diagram of Figure 1 shows the major components of the DS18B20. The DS18B20 has four main data components:

- 64-bit lasered ROM,
- temperature sensor,
- non-volatile temperature alarm triggers TH and TL, and
- a configuration registers.

The device derives its power from the 1-Wire communication line by storing energy on an internal capacitor during periods of time when the signal line is high and continues to operate off this power source during the low times of the 1-Wire line until it returns high to replenish the parasite (capacitor) supply. As an alternative, the DS18B20 may also be powered from an external 3 volt - 5.5-volt supply. Communication to the DS18B20 is via a 1-Wire port. With the 1-Wire port, the memory and control functions will not be available before the ROM function protocol has been established. The master must first provide one of five ROM function commands:

- Read ROM,
- Match ROM,
- Search ROM,
- Skip ROM,
- Alarm Search.

These commands operate on the 64-bit lasered ROM portion of each device and can single out a specific device if many are present on the 1-Wire line as well as indicate to the bus master how many and what types of devices are present. After a ROM function sequence has been successfully executed, the memory and control functions are accessible and the master may then provide any one of the six memory and control function commands. One control function

command instructs the DS18B20 to perform a temperature measurement. The result of this measurement will be placed in the DS18B20's scratch-pad memory, and may be read by issuing a memory function command which reads the contents of the scratchpad memory. The temperature alarm triggers TH and TL consist of 1-byte EEPROM each. If the alarm search command is not applied to the DS18B20, these registers may be used as general-purpose user memory. The scratchpad also contains a configuration byte to set the desired resolution of the temperature to digital conversion. Writing TH, TL, and the configuration byte is done using a memory function command. Read access to these registers is through the scratchpad. All data is read and written least significant bit first.

Figure 1: shows the block diagram of the major components of the DS18B20.

A parasite (capacitor) is powered by the 1-Wire communication line by storing energy in a capacitor internally during periods of time when the signal line is high and continuing to operate from the capacitor during low times of the 1-Wire line until it returns to a high level to replenish the parasite supply.

2.1 Parasite Power

The block diagram (Figure 1) shows the parasite-powered circuitry. This circuitry “steals” power whenever the DQ or VDD pins are high. DQ will provide sufficient power as long as the specified timing and voltage requirements are met (see the section titled “1-Wire Bus System”). The advantages of parasite power are twofold: 1) by parasiting off this pin, no local power source is needed for remote sensing of temperature, and 2) the ROM may be read in absence of normal power. In order for the DS18B20 to be able to perform accurate temperature conversions, sufficient power must be provided over the DQ line when a temperature conversion is taking place. Since the operating current of the DS18B20 is up to 1.5 mA, the DQ line will not have sufficient drive due to the 5k pullup resistor. This problem is particularly acute if several DS18B20s are on the same DQ and attempting to convert simultaneously.

There are two ways to assure that the DS18B20 has sufficient supply current during its active conversion cycle. The first is to provide a strong pullup on the DQ line whenever temperature conversions or copies to the E2 memory are taking place. This may be accomplished by using a MOSFET to pull the DQ line directly to the power supply as shown in Figure 2. The DQ line must be switched over to the strong pullup within 10 μ s maximum after issuing any protocol that involves copying to the E2 memory or initiates temperature conversions. When using the parasite power mode, the VDD pin must be tied to ground. Another method of supplying current to the DS18B20 is through the use of an external power supply tied to the VDD pin, as shown in Figure 3. The advantage to this is that the strong pullup is not required on the DQ line, and the bus master need not be tied up holding that line high during temperature conversions. This allows other data traffic on the 1-Wire bus during the conversion time. In

addition, any number of DS18B20s may be placed on the 1-Wire bus, and if they all use external power, they may all simultaneously perform temperature conversions by issuing the Skip ROM command and then issuing the Convert T command. Note that as long as the external power supply is active, the GND pin may not be floating. The use of parasite power is not recommended above 100°C, since it may not be able to sustain communications given the higher leakage currents the DS18B20 exhibits at these temperatures. For applications in which such temperatures are likely, it is strongly recommended that VDD be applied to the DS18B20.

For situations where the bus master does not know whether the DS18B20s on the bus are parasite powered or supplied with external VDD, a provision is made in the DS18B20 to signal the power supply scheme used. The bus master can determine if any DS18B20s are on the bus which require the strong pullup by sending a Skip ROM protocol, then issuing the read power supply command. After this command is issued, the master then issues read time slots. The DS18B20 will send back “0” on the 1-Wire bus if it is parasite powered; it will send back a “1” if it is powered from the VDD pin. If the master receives a “0,” it knows that it must supply the strong pullup on the DQ line during temperature conversions. See “Memory Command Functions” section for more detail on this command protocol.

Figure 2: strong pullup for supplying DS18B20 during temperature conversion

Figure 3: using V_{DD} to supply temperature conversion current

3. Operation - Measuring Temperature

The core functionality of the DS18B20 is its direct-to-digital temperature sensor. The resolution of the DS18B20 is configurable (9, 10, 11, or 12 bits), with 12-bit readings the factory default state. This equates to a temperature resolution of 0.5°C, 0.25°C, 0.125°C, or 0.0625°C. Following the issuance of the Convert T [44h] command, a temperature conversion

is performed and the thermal data is stored in the scratchpad memory in a 16-bit, sign-extended two's complement format. The temperature information can be retrieved over the 1-Wire interface by issuing a Read Scratchpad [BEh] command once the conversion has been performed. The data is transferred over the 1-Wire bus, LSB first. The MSB of the temperature register contains the "sign" (S) bit, denoting whether the temperature is positive or negative. Table 2 describes the exact relationship of output data to measured temperature. The table assumes 12-bit resolution. If the DS18B20 is configured for a lower resolution, insignificant bits will contain zeros. For Fahrenheit usage, a lookup table or conversion routine must be used.

Table 2: Temperature/Data Relationships

2^3	2^2	2^1	2^0	2^{-1}	2^{-2}	2^{-3}	2^{-4}	LSb
MSb			(Unit = °C)				LSb	
s	s	s	s	s	2^6	2^5	2^4	MSb

3.1. Operation - Alarm Signalling

After the DS18B20 has performed a temperature conversion, the temperature value is compared to the trigger values stored in TH and TL. Since these registers are 8-bit only, bits 9-12 are ignored for comparison. The most significant bit of TH or TL directly corresponds to the sign bit of the 16-bit temperature register. If the result of a temperature measurement is higher than TH or lower than TL, an alarm flag inside the device is set. This flag is updated with every temperature measurement. As long as the alarm flag is set, the DS18B20 will respond to the alarm search command. This allows many DS18B20s to be connected in parallel doing simultaneous temperature measurements. If somewhere the temperature exceeds the limits, the alarming device(s) can be identified and read immediately without having to read non-alarming devices.

3.2 64-Bit Lasered Rom

Each DS18B20 contains a unique ROM code that is 64-bits long. The first 8 bits are a 1-Wire family code (DS18B20 code is 28h). The next 48 bits are a unique serial number. The last 8 bits are a CRC of the first 56 bits. (See Figure 4.) The 64-bit ROM and ROM Function Control section allow the DS18B20 to operate as a 1-Wire device and follow the 1-Wire protocol detailed in the section "1-Wire Bus System." The functions required to control sections of the DS18B20 are not accessible until the ROM function protocol has been satisfied. This protocol is described in the ROM function protocol flowchart (Figure 5). The 1-Wire bus master must first provide one of five ROM function commands: 1) Read ROM, 2) Match ROM, 3) Search ROM, 4) Skip ROM, or 5) Alarm Search. After a ROM function sequence has been successfully executed, the functions specific to the DS18B20 are accessible and the bus master may then provide one of the six memory and control function commands.

3.3 CRC Generation

The DS18B20 has an 8-bit CRC stored in the most significant byte of the 64-bit ROM. The bus master can compute a CRC value from the first 56-bits of the 64-bit ROM and compare it to the value stored within the DS18B20 to determine if the ROM data has been received error-free by the bus master. The equivalent polynomial function of this CRC is:

$$\text{CRC} = X^8 + X^5 + X^4 + 1$$

The DS18B20 also generates an 8-bit CRC value using the same polynomial function shown above and provides this value to the bus master to validate the transfer of data bytes. In each case where a CRC is used for data transfer validation, the bus master must calculate a CRC value using the polynomial function given above and compare the calculated value to either the 8-bit CRC value stored in the 64-bit ROM portion of the DS18B20 (for ROM reads) or the 8-bit CRC value computed within the DS18B20 (which is read as a ninth byte when the scratchpad is read). The comparison of CRC values and decision to continue with an operation are determined entirely by the bus master. There is no circuitry inside the DS18B20 that prevents a command sequence from proceeding if the CRC stored in or calculated by the DS18B20 does not match the value generated by the bus master.

The 1-Wire CRC can be generated using a polynomial generator consisting of a shift register and XOR gates as shown in Figure 6. Additional information about the Dallas 1-Wire Cyclic Redundancy Check is available in Application Note 27 entitled “Understanding and Using Cyclic Redundancy Checks with Dallas Semiconductor Touch Memory Products.” The shift register bits are initialized to 0. Then starting with the least significant bit of the family code, 1 bit at a time is shifted in. After the 8th bit of the family code has been entered, then the serial number is entered. After the 48th bit of the serial number has been entered, the shift register contains the CRC value. Shifting in the 8 bits of CRC should return the shift register to all 0s.

4. Memory

The DS18B20’s memory is organized as shown in Figure 8. The memory consists of a scratchpad RAM and a non-volatile, electrically erasable (E2) RAM, which stores the high and low temperature triggers TH and TL, and the configuration register. The scratchpad helps ensure data integrity when communicating over the 1-Wire bus. Data is first written to the scratchpad using the Write Scratchpad [4Eh] command. It can then be verified by using the Read Scratchpad [BEh] command. After the data has been verified, a Copy Scratchpad [48h] command will transfer the data to the non-volatile (E2) RAM. This process ensures data integrity when modifying memory. The DS18B20 EEPROM is rated for a minimum of 50,000 writes and 10 years data retention at $T = +55^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The scratchpad is organized as eight bytes of memory. The first 2 bytes contain the LSB and the MSB of the measured temperature information, respectively. The third and fourth bytes are volatile copies of TH and TL and are refreshed with every power-on reset. The fifth byte is a volatile copy of the configuration register and is refreshed with every power-on reset. The configuration register will be explained in more detail later in this section of the datasheet. The sixth, seventh, and eighth bytes are used for internal computations, and thus will not read out any predictable pattern.

It is imperative that one writes TH, TL, and config in succession; i.e., a write is not valid if one writes only to TH and TL, for example, and then issues a reset. If any of these bytes must be written, all three must be written before a reset is issued. There is a ninth byte which may be read with a Read Scratchpad [BEh] command. This byte contains a cyclic redundancy check (CRC) byte which is the CRC over all of the eight previous bytes. This CRC is implemented in the fashion described in the section titled “CRC Generation”.

5. One-wire bus system

The one-Wire bus is a system which has a single bus master and one or more slaves. The DS18B20 behaves as a slave. The discussion of this bus system is broken down into three

topics: hardware configuration, transaction sequence, and one-Wire signalling (signal types and timing).

- The main advantage of 1 wire protocol is that we can control multiple 1-wire devices via a single pin of Microcontroller.
- You must have heard of the master-slave system, where 1 master device can control or communicate with all slave devices.
- 1-wire protocol follows a similar master-slave system, where microcontroller acts as a master and all our 1-wire devices e.g., DS18B20 act as slaves.
- If we have interfaced only one device with our microcontroller then such a system is called a single drop but if we interface multiple 1-wire devices via a single pin then it's called multidrop system.

Now let's have a better understanding of One Wire System from the figure given below:

Figure 4. One wire Bus System

6. Hardware configuration

The 1-Wire bus has only a single line by definition; it is important that each device on the bus be able to drive it at the appropriate time. To facilitate this, each device attached to the 1-Wire bus must have open drain or 3-state outputs. The 1-Wire port of the DS18B20 (DQ pin) is open drain with an internal circuit equivalent to that shown in Figure 5. A multidrop bus consists of a 1-Wire bus with multiple slaves attached. The 1-Wire bus requires a pullup resistor of approximately 5 kΩ.

Figure 5. Hardware configuration

The idle state for the 1-Wire bus is high. If for any reason a transaction needs to be suspended, the bus must be left in the idle state if the transaction is to resume. Infinite recovery time can occur between bits so long as the 1-Wire bus is in the inactive (high) state during the recovery period. If this does not occur and the bus is left low for more than 480 μs, all components on the bus will be reset.

7. Conclusion

These one-wire digital temperature sensors are fairly precise ($\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ over much of the range) and can give up to 12 bits of precision from the onboard digital-to-analogy converter. They work great with any microcontroller using a single digital pin, and you can even connect multiple ones to the same pin, each one has a unique 64-bit ID burned in at the factory to differentiate them. Usable with 3.0-5.0V systems. The only downside is they use 1-Wire protocol, which is somewhat complex, and requires a bunch of code to parse out the communication. Temperature is one of the most basic environmental parameters. The measurement and control of temperature are of great significance and application value in people's daily life and industrial production. In the temperature measurement methods, the traditional mercury or kerosene thermometer has the character of low accuracy, slow speed and not convenient. While non-contact infrared temperature measurement has relatively low accuracy, and the sensor is expensive, the price is not high. In contrast, the digital temperature sensor developed in recent years has been widely used in industrial measurement, environmental temperature detection and other fields because of its high precision, low price and easy to measure. Based on this, the DS18B20 digital temperature sensor, LCD display and expanded keyboard, are used for the design of the digital temperature measuring system, and the experimental tested for the measurement system is executed.

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